

Isolation, Identification and Characterization of Hydrocarbon-Degrading Bacteria in Top and Subsoil of Mechanic Workshops in Gusau, Zamfara

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Abstract

The soil in mechanic workshops contains diverse hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria. This research aimed to isolate and characterize these bacteria in Gusau, Zamfara. Samples from Labin-Labin Motor Garage, Yar'dole Garage, Gangeren-Yarima Garage, and Unguwar-Dallatu Garage were collected, this include four samples of top and subsoil, at depths of 5cm and 10cm, respectively. Using the spread plate method, total hydrocarbon counts ranged from 1×10^5 cfu/g to 5.7×10^5 cfu/g in topsoil and 1.2×10^5 cfu/g to 8.2×10^5 cfu/g in subsoil. The highest counts were in Labin-Labin Motor Garage for the topsoil and Gangeren-Yarima for the subsoil. *Bacillus* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Streptococcus* spp., and *Staphylococcus* spp. were isolated with *Bacillus* spp. exhibiting the highest hydrocarbon degradation efficiency through 2,6-dichlorophenolindophenol (DCPIP) tests (0.462nm to 1.501nm). Soil samples from mechanic workshops indicated contamination with hydrocarbons, underscoring the importance of bacteria in potential biodegradation. In conclusion, *Bacillus* spp. is identified as a key hydrocarbon degrader, and the study recommends these isolates for possible use in bioremediation of hydrocarbons in mechanic workshops. This research sheds light on the ecological role of bacteria in contaminated soils, providing insights into environmental management and remediation strategies.

Keywords: Hydrocarbon, bacteria, mechanic, workshop

1.0 Introduction

Soil is a dynamic ecosystem that sustains life by fostering a delicate balance of inorganic particles, organic matter, minerals, gases, liquids, and a myriad of organisms [1]. Mechanic workshops are vital for vehicle maintenance but pose environmental threats due to the improper disposal of petroleum substances, emerging as major contributors to hydrocarbon pollution [2].

Petroleum-based products are integral to daily life and industry and consist of intricate mixtures of aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbons, contributing to environmental pollution during transportation and distribution activities [3, 4]. The discharge of used oil from vehicles, common in mechanic workshops, alters soil texture and microbiological properties, escalating environmental challenges [5]. Leakage of gasoline and the presence of diesel, petroleum, and engine oil in mechanic workshop soils

contribute to chronic health hazards, including liver or kidney diseases, bone marrow damage, and an increased risk of cancer [6,7]

Hydrocarbon-contaminated soil poses significant risks to human health, especially when contaminants reach drinking water sources. Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene, ubiquitous hydrocarbons, exhibit high mobility and have the potential to easily contaminate water resources, thereby posing carcinogenic risks. [8]. Unregulated practices in mechanic workshops, including spills, illegal dumping, and careless handling of petroleum products, pose substantial environmental and health risks. Continuous releases of pollutants, such as petrol, diesel, and lubricants, contaminate soil and groundwater, potentially leading to chronic health hazards [9]. This study aims to isolate, identify, and characterize hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria in the top and subsoil of mechanic workshops in Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria. The research

addresses the environmental consequences of hydrocarbon contamination, focusing on soil microbiological properties.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 The Study Area

The study was carried out in Microbiology laboratory in Federal University Gusau. The samples were collected from 4 different mechanic workshops within Gusau metropolis located in the North-west of Nigeria. This is located between latitude 12.09°N-12.5°N and longitude 6.67°E with an area of 5,364Km. The inhabitants are mainly civil servant, farmers, petty traders and commercial workers.

2.2 Sample Collection

Eight (8) samples, which comprised of four top soil and four sub soil were collected from four (4) different locations which are: Labin-labin motor garage, Yar'dole garage, Gangeren-Yarima garage and Unguwar-Dallatu garage within Gusau metropolis, Zamfara State. The soil samples for hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria analysis were collected into a sterile polyethylene bag using a digger from a depth of 0-5cm for the top soil and 15cm for the sub-soil both down the horizon. The samples were transported to the laboratory within 1hr of collection and analyzed within 24hrs.

2.3 Serial Dilution

Five (5) folds of serial dilution was carried out as described by Chessbrough [10]. One gram of the homogenized top and sub- soil were introduced into a 9ml sterile distilled water. This test tube was placed in an orbital shaker for 24 hours to achieve a proper homogenization [11]. After which the test tube was allowed to cool, then 1ml of the homogenized sample was transferred into a second test tube containing 9ml of sterile water. This was repeated until the fifth test tube.

2.4 Sample preparation and Inoculation

The top and sub-soil samples which were collected at different Mechanic workshops in Gusau metropolis, were air-dried in the Microbiology laboratory. This helps in removing excess moisture from the soil samples. Excessive moisture can interfere with the subsequent processes, such as homogenization and sieving, and may also affect the accuracy of microbial

analysis. Afterwards the samples were homogenized by grounding with a mortar and pestle, then it was sieved through a 2mm stainless steel which was sterilized in an autoclave at 121°C for 15 minutes so as to remove debris. One gram of both the topsoil and the subsoil were weighed and diluted with 10mls of water. The serial dilution was done in five (5) folds. A volume of 0.1ml was collected from dilute 10^{-2} and was spread on a sterile Mineral salt medium plate using a bent glass rod. Only one medium was used based on the specific objectives and focus of the study. Mineral salt medium selectively supports the growth of bacteria capable of utilizing hydrocarbons as a carbon source. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours and the cultured plates were sub-cultured. Pure isolates were stored in a Nutrient agar slant and kept for further identification.

2.5 Bacteriological Analysis

2.5.1 Total hydrocarbon degrading bacteria count

Mineral salt media was prepared according to manufactures instruction and was sterilized in an autoclave at 15 PSI (121°C) for 15mins. It was allowed to cool and aseptically dispensed into the petri dish, then 0.1ml of the appropriate 5-fold serial dilution (10^{-2}) was inoculated into a sterile plate using spread plate method. Duplicate plate were prepared and labeled for the 8 soil samples, then they were incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. After which the colonies were counted using colony counter.

2.6 Characterization and Identification of the Isolates

Bacterial isolates were identified and characterized base on morphological and biochemical characteristics. The biochemical tests were carried out as described by Cheesbrough [10]. The tests were catalase, oxidase, coagulase, citrate, indole, motility triple sugar iron, methyl red, voges-proskauer and hydrogen sulphide production. They were identified according to the scheme of Krieg and Holt [12].

2.7 Hydrocarbon Degrading Test: Bacteria isolates were inoculated separately into 5ml nutrient broth medium, and were incorporated with 50µl of diesel as hydrocarbon substrate.

Then, 40µl of (DCPIP) 2,6- Dichlorophenol-indophenol was added. The media were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Discolouration of DCPIP was observed qualitatively after 24, 48 and 72 hours. In oxidized form DCPIP was blue, whereas in reduced form DCPIP was colourless as described by Hason et al. [13].

2.8 Screening for hydrocarbon degrading bacteria: The pure bacteria isolates were inoculated into a solidified mineral salt agar containing 5ml of crude oil as the sole carbon source. The isolates were incubated at 30°C for 24, 48 and 72hrs. Afterwards, the absorbance of each sample was measured at a wavelength of 600nm using a spectrophotometer.

3.0 Results

The results of this research illustrating the total hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria count in soil samples from both topsoil and subsoil across four mechanic workshops in Gusau metropolis, are presented in Table 1. Among the topsoil samples, Labin-Labin Motor Garage exhibited the highest bacterial count at 5.7×10^5 CFU/g, while Yar'dole Garage had the lowest at 1.0×10^5 CFU/g. Conversely, within the subsoil samples, Yar'dole Garage recorded the highest bacterial count at

8.2×10^5 CFU/g, while Gangeren-Yarima Garage showed the lowest count at 1.2×10^5 CFU/g. Notably, Unguwar-Dallatu Garage showed the absence of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria.

Table 1: Total hydrocarbon degrading bacteria of the mechanic workshop soil

Location	Top soil (CFU/g)	Sub-soil (CFU/g)
LL	5.7×10^5	3.4×10^5
GY	1.89×10^5	1.2×10^5
YD	1.0×10^5	8.2×10^5
UD	No growth	No growth

Key: LL = Labin-labin motor garage, YD= Yar'dole garage, GY = Gangeren-Yarima garage, UD = Unguwar-Dallatu garage.

The morphological and biochemical characteristics of bacteria isolated from soil samples are detailed in Table 2. The isolated bacteria include *Pseudomonas* spp, *Bacillus* spp, *Staphylococcus* spp, and *Streptococcus* spp.

Table 2: Morphological and Biochemical Characteristics Isolates from the Mechanic Workshops

Isolate Code	Morphological characteristic	Gram stain reaction	Biochemical Tests							Possible organism
			Cat	Cit	Ur	In	MR	VP	Mot	
HDB-1	Large, rod, entire, wrinkled and creamy	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	<i>Bacillus</i> spp
HDB-2	irregular, bluish green, rough, small, and rod	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp
HBD-3	Small, circular and yellow	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.
HBD-4	Round, semi-transparent opaque and light yellow	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	<i>Streptococcus</i> spp.

Key: + = positive, - = Negative

Cat = Catalase, Cit = Citrate Utilization, Ur = Urease, In = Indole, MR = Methyl Red, VP = Voges-Proskauer, Mot = Motility, HBD = Hydrocarbon degrading bacteria.

The screening of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria were measured by absorbance at a wavelength of 600nm using spectrophotometer on different culture media, is presented in Table 4.3 At the conclusion of the 72-hour period, *Bacillus* spp.

exhibited the highest absorbance at 1.501nm, followed by *Staphylococcus* spp. at 1.192nm, *Streptococcus* spp. at 0.856nm, and *Pseudomonas* spp. at 0.790nm.

Table 3: Screening of hydrocarbon degrading bacteria present in the mechanic workshop

Isolates	Absorbance (at wavelength 600 nm)		
	24hrs	48hrs	72hrs
<i>Bacillus</i> spp.	0.462	1.245	1.501
<i>Pseudomonas</i> spp.	0.111	0.574	0.790
<i>Staphylococcus</i> spp.	0.224	0.942	1.192
<i>Streptococcus</i> spp.	0.292	0.645	0.856

4.0 Discussion

Hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria counts were isolated and analyzed at various mechanic workshops in Gusau metropolis. Among the topsoil samples obtained, Labin-Labin Motor Garage exhibited the highest mean bacterial count of 5.7×10^5 CFU/g, while the topsoil sample from Yar'dole garage had the least mean bacterial count of 1.0×10^5 CFU/g. The significant disparity in mean bacterial counts underscores the diversity and activity of microorganisms in distinct garage environments. The elevated count in Labin-Labin Motor Garage suggests conditions more conducive to bacterial growth and proliferation.

In contrast, the subsoil samples from Yar'dole garage registered the highest bacterial count of 8.2×10^5 CFU/mg, while the subsoil from Gangeren-Yarima garage displayed the lowest bacterial count at 1.2×10^5 CFU/g. Bacterial counts often serve as indicators of soil quality and fertility, with the higher count in the subsoil of Yar'dole garage implying potentially favorable conditions for microbial life, influencing soil fertility and nutrient cycling.

The observed higher hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria count in the subsoil compared to the topsoil could be attributed to past contamination events or activities, contributing to the accumulation of hydrocarbons in the subsoil over time. Hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria in the subsoil may have adapted to these historical conditions. Additionally, the penetration of hydrocarbons deeper into the soil profile and the

subsoil acting as a reservoir for hydrocarbons may sustain higher concentrations, supporting the growth of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria.

This finding contradicts the result reported by Ebakota et al. [14]; in their study on the isolation and characterization of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria within the top and subsoil of selected mechanic workshops in Benin City metropolis, Nigeria. According to their findings, the topsoil exhibited a higher bacteria count, reaching 2.94×10^6 CFU/g as the highest count, compared to the subsoil, which recorded the highest count at 1.0×10^6 CFU/g. It also disagrees with the findings of Azuwike et al. [15], who recorded total hydrocarbon bacteria count at the ranges of 1.30×10^3 to 2.80×10^6 CFU/g in Owerri, Imo State.

The bacteria isolated from the top and sub soil of the hydrocarbon contaminated soil samples were *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp. and *Streptococcus* spp. These organisms have been reported to utilize hydrocarbon, particularly *Pseudomonas* spp. and *Bacillus* spp. This is similar to the finding of Ebakota et al. [14] who also isolated *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp. and *Streptococcus* spp. from both the top and sub soil of selected mechanic workshops in Benin City metropolis, Nigeria. It contradicts the finding of Azuwike et al. [15], who isolated four species of bacteria, namely, *Enterococcus*, *Micrococcus*, *Staphylococcus* and *Bacillus* spp. from Owerri, Imo state.

Pseudomonas spp. are a group of bacteria that are known for their ability to thrive in diverse

environments. They are often found in soil, water, and various man-made environments, including mechanic workshops. Mechanic workshops tends to provide a variety of nutrients that support bacterial growth. Oil spills, lubricants, and other organic materials present in a workshop environment can serve as a nutrient source for *Pseudomonas* spp. This organism is known for its resistance to various environmental stresses, including chemicals and pollutants that may be present in a mechanic workshop [16].

Bacillus spp. are a diverse group of bacteria that are commonly found in soil and various environments. The presence of *Bacillus* spp. in a mechanic workshop can be attributed to dust and particles often generated from activities such as metal grinding, sanding, and other mechanical processes within the Mechanic workshops. *Bacillus* spp. can be present in airborne dust and settle in different areas [17]. Also tools, machinery, and equipment in a mechanic workshop can harbor *Bacillus* spp. if not properly cleaned and maintained. Residual grease, oil, or other organic materials may provide a nutrient source for these bacteria.

Staphylococcus spp. are normal inhabitants of the skin and mucous membranes of humans [18]. Mechanics working in the workshop may introduce these bacteria through skin contact and the shedding of skin cells. *Staphylococci* can persist on surfaces and tools. If these surfaces are not regularly cleaned and disinfected, *Staphylococcus* spp. may find suitable conditions for survival. Also, materials brought into the workshop, such as clothing or personal items, may carry *Staphylococcus* spp. This can contribute to the contamination of the environment.

Streptococcus spp. are normal inhabitants of the human respiratory and oral microbiota [18]. Mechanics and other individuals working in the workshop may introduce these bacteria through respiratory droplets or by shedding them from their oral cavity. Tools, equipment, and surfaces in the workshop can become contaminated with *Streptococcus* spp. through contact with respiratory secretions, saliva, or other bodily fluids. Items brought into the workshop, such as clothing, personal protective equipment, or food containers, may carry *Streptococcus* spp., leading to contamination of the environment.

The observed results in the screening of hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria using a

spectrophotometer indicated varying degrees of absorbance, which can be correlated with the metabolic activity of the bacteria in degrading hydrocarbons. The differences in absorbance values are reflective of the extent to which each bacterial species has participated in hydrocarbon degradation during the 72-hour screening period.

Specifically, *Bacillus* spp. exhibited the highest absorbance at 1.501nm, suggesting a robust hydrocarbon-degrading activity. This may be attributed to the inherent metabolic capabilities of *Bacillus* spp., including their ability to produce enzymes or other biochemical compounds that facilitate the breakdown of hydrocarbons.

Staphylococcus spp. followed with an absorbance of 1.192nm, indicating a substantial but slightly lower level of hydrocarbon degradation compared to *Bacillus* spp. Similarly, *Streptococcus* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp. showed absorbance values of 0.856nm and 0.790nm, respectively. These values suggest varying degrees of hydrocarbon-degrading potential among these bacterial species.

This result complies with work carried out by Nwachukwu et al. [19] and Arotupin and Ogunmalu [20], who reported *Pseudomonas* spp. and *Bacillus* spp. as organisms involved in hydrocarbon degradation of Nbugka mechanic workshop, Nnewi. It contradicts the findings of Ebakota et al. [14], who reported *Pseudomonas* spp. to degrade hydrocarbon at a wavelength of 0.725nm, and *Bacillus* spp. at a wavelength of 0.889nm in selected mechanic workshops in Benin City.

The absorbance values obtained from the spectrophotometric analysis reflect the efficacy of the different bacterial species in degrading hydrocarbons. The higher absorbance values indicate greater metabolic activity and efficiency in utilizing hydrocarbons as energy sources for bacterial growth. The discovery of these microorganisms in these settings indicates their capacity to adapt to the environment and exploit certain substances as energy sources. The occurrence of *Bacillus* species may be linked to their capability to generate spores, facilitating survival in diverse environments, including soils contaminated with hydrocarbons [20].

5.0 Conclusions

The results of this study revealed the presence of diverse bacteria with the ability to degrade

hydrocarbons, emphasizing the significance of understanding microbial ecology in such environments. The findings indicated variations in hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria counts between topsoil and subsoil samples, with Labin-Labin Motor Garage exhibiting the highest count in the topsoil, and Yar'dole Garage showing the highest count in the subsoil. This discrepancy suggests the importance of considering soil depth and historical contamination events when assessing the microbial response to hydrocarbons. The isolated bacterial species, including *Pseudomonas* spp., *Bacillus* spp., *Staphylococcus* spp., and *Streptococcus* spp., demonstrated their adaptability to hydrocarbon-contaminated environments. *Bacillus* spp. exhibited the highest absorbance, indicating robust hydrocarbon-degrading activity, followed by *Staphylococcus* spp., *Streptococcus* spp. and *Pseudomonas* spp.

6.0 Recommendations

Future research could delve deeper into the specific mechanisms employed by these bacteria in hydrocarbon degradation and explore practical applications for bioremediation in mechanic workshop soils. Additionally, assessing the impact of environmental factors on microbial community dynamics would enhance the ability to optimize biodegradation processes.

7.0 Acknowledgments

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8.0 Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest. This manuscript has not been published or presented elsewhere in part or in entirety and is not under consideration by another journal. We have read and understood the journal policies, and we believe that neither the manuscript nor the study violates any of these. Both authors have been personally and actively involved in substantive work leading to the manuscript and will hold themselves jointly and individually responsible for its content. All co-authors agreed to submit this manuscript.

9.0 References

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